

RefSciRate: A reference rating method for single scientific papers

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Introduction

The evaluation of scientific papers has become an important subject in library and information science. For a long time, citation frequency-based measures have dominated the evaluation of papers, but they treat all citations equally, ignoring their varying contributions or appraisals. If the different levels of importance for citations can be identified, we have the potential to enhance citation frequency-based bibliometrics by integrating a citation importance value. In previous related studies, Wan et al. (2014) proposed a regression method using key features to estimate citation strength; Zhu et al. (2015) automatically identified influential references in a bibliography. Building upon these studies, our work proposes a novel reference rating method for individual scientific papers that emphasizes the content level of the citation. Citation context, which is called “citance” by Nakov et al. (2004), refers to the context near the reference mark when an article cites other documents. Valuable citation sentences can truly reflect the significance of the paper to scientific development. Thus, we employ a semantic analysis of citances to better understand the author's intention in referencing a source in their article. By integrating citance with other pertinent indicators, this approach enables a comprehensive evaluation of the reference's significance in the article.

To be more precise, we propose a reference importance rating method to rate all references in a scientific paper into 4 levels according to their importance for the paper by examining the relevant count features, position features and contextual features. We call this method as RefSciRate. We leverage Pearson correlation coefficient to perform feature selection, and utilize grid search method for features further filtering and optimal feature weight determination. In order to verify the effectiveness of our method, we have manually constructed two datasets for experiments, and the evaluation results show that the estimated values can achieve a good consistency with human-labeled values. Our proposed method can be an excellent supplement to the process of assessing articles based solely on citation frequency.

Method

This section focuses on the method used by RefSciRate to rate all references for each article. It includes the selection of rating features, the design idea of feature weights, and the evaluation of the rating method.

13 features are selected for rating references from the perspectives of count, position and context of citations. They are *count of in-text mentions* (F1), *count of in-text enumeration* (F2), *citation length* (F3), *textual similarity* (F4), citation importance (F5: *neutral citation*, F6: *non-neutral citation*), citation intention (F7: *background citation*, F8: *method citation*, F9: *result comparison citation*), and location of citations (F10-F13). Features F10-F13 calculate the number of times a citation appears in each position (background, method, result, conclusion) in the citing document. It should be noted that we define F2 as a weighted metric of F1, for example, if a reference is mentioned a total of 2 times in the citing document, once alone and once together with k references, then its in-text enumeration is $(1+1/k)$. And F4 calculates the similarities between the citances and the corresponding sentences in the abstract of the citing paper. All the rating features are normalized to the interval $[0, 1]$ to ensure the uniformity of the indices' value range.

To further seek which features play a significant role in determining the importance of a reference, we calculate the Pearson correlation coefficients (PCC) between the different features and references' importance levels. Then we propose a formula to calculate the reference rating, as shown in (1), by assigning different weights to each feature to calculate the final level.

$$R = \sum_i^n w_i f_i \quad (1)$$

where w_i represents the weight of the i -th feature, f_i means the value of the corresponding feature, and R represents the sum of all the weights. We would divide the R -values into 4 bands according to the subsequent actual situation, which would be used as the four rating levels in this paper.

Data

There is currently no public assessment established for reference rating. Under this circumstance, we

construct two datasets to annotate the above features and test the performance of the proposed rating framework in our paper.

Dataset 1: This dataset comes from the gold-standard dataset published in the study of Zhu et al. (2015). The authors of the gold-standard dataset indicated which references in each paper were influential for them. However, only 30 papers are randomly selected from initial 100 as Dataset 1 for validation owing to the unavailability and duplication for some articles, and the removal of some review articles.

Dataset 2: This dataset only includes 5 papers, with the addition that a rating between 1 and 4 must be assigned to each reference. We invite three domain-related researchers to rate all the references referring to the following criteria:

Level 1: The reference is usually not related to the article but is merely a description of some macro background knowledge. The citance is usually short and may appear together with several references.

Level 2: The reference is typically relevant to the article (e.g., subject context) and just lists a few references that have minimal bearing on the article.

Level 3: The reference is generally relevant to the article (e.g., the scope of the research), but the content cited is not very important.

Level 4: The reference is pertinent to the subject of the article and is elaborately detailed, it may be mentioned many times throughout the full text.

Results

Figure 1 displays the PCC between features and the importance of references on the two datasets. By adding features one by one based on their decreasing PCC, we construct feature combinations and evaluate the influence of their references. The best feature subset is identified as the point where further addition of features would result in decreased performance. In the case of each combination of features, a grid search method is used to determine the optimal weights for that feature group. The F-measure and error value (Mean Squared Error, MSE) are applied to evaluate the performance of the RefSciRate model as a classification problem (influential or non-influential) and a regression problem (4 levels of reference rating), respectively. The experimental results on Dataset 1 show that the F-measure reached a maximum of 0.5844 when we add features {F1, F3, F5}, which is superior to the optimal result in the study of Zhu et al. (2015) by 0.16, while the MSE reached its minimum value of 0.1423 at this point. When we continue to add features F10 and F2, the MSE value does not change, but the F-measure decreases slightly. On Dataset 2, we only measure MSE and find the best minimum value of 0.2784 when we add the features {F11, F2, F5, F3}.

According to the results, the situation in which some features are not chosen implies that they may be not as suitable for estimating how much importance a reference occupies in an article. Combining the sets of key features of Dataset 1 and Dataset 2, we believe that the factors set that have a considerable impact on the importance rating of references is {F1, F2, F3, F5}. These four features all appear in the two selected feature subgroups, indicating that they play a leading role in rating the importance of references.

Figure 1. PCC between features and the importance of references on Dataset1 (Left) and Dataset2 (Right)

Conclusion

This paper focuses on the creation of a rating method named as RefSciRate for all references' importance in a single scientific paper, which provides readers with a novel perspective on interpreting a paper. Our work offers a first glance at how to design a reference rating method based on citance and its associated features in the full text. Although the experiments show promising results, the RefSciRate method suffers from several limitations. For instance, the two validation datasets we used are small in size. This is a direction for our future work.

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